

orange CHAB formed was filtered and crystallised from ethanol/methanol.

Metal complexes: Copper(II) and nickel(II) complexes were prepared by refluxing the solutions of metal chlorides with CHAB in alcohol. A little sodium acetate was added⁶. The Fe(II) complex was prepared by refluxing a solution of ferrous ammonium sulphate with CHAB in alcohol in an atmosphere of hydrogen. The excess of metal or ligand was removed by washing with hot distilled water⁷. The Cu(II) complex is reddish yellow while those of Ni(II) and Fe(II) are yellow and reddish brown, respectively.

Indicator solution: The indicator solution was prepared by dissolving 200 mg of a complex in 100 ml methanol. Freshly prepared 0.2% solutions were used as indicators.

Method of titration:

10 ml 0.1 M hydrochloric acid was pipetted into a conical flask and about 0.5 ml 0.2% indicator solution was added. The acid was then titrated against 0.1 M sodium hydroxide solution. The sharp colour change from colourless to turmeric yellow was the end point.

Results and Discussion

Titration precision:

Eight titrations were performed with each indicator and the ability of the indicators to change colour was tested. The precision obtained from each set is given below:

Indicator	Maximum deviation from the mean	Average deviation from the mean
Cu(II)-CHAB complex	0.05%	0.05%
Ni(II)-CHAB complex	0.05%	0.05%
Fe(II)-CHAB complex	0.05%	0.05%

Effect of the concentration of indicators:

Changing the concentration of the indicator solution from 0.2 to 0.5% in all the cases did not affect the titration results. So, 0.5 ml 0.2% indicator solution is recommended for titration. Less than 0.5 ml of the indicator gives false end points due to indistinguishable colour change.

pH and temperature range for colour change:

It has been found that the pH range for colour change is 6.5 to 8.0 for the said complexes. The titration of strong acid and strong base can be carried out in the 25 to 40° temperature range.

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Polarographic Studies of Acetylacetonate Complexes of Pb(II) and Mn(II)

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IN aqueous solutions acetylacetonate is a weak acid with a pK_a value¹⁻⁴ of 8.95. It readily forms⁵ stable metal chelates. Branica and coworkers⁶⁻¹⁰ undertook polarographic investigations of acetylacetonate complexes of UO₂(II), Cu(II), Co(II) and Ni(II). Aihara and Misumi¹¹ studied polarographic behaviour of Ni(II), Cr(III) and Co(II) acetylacetonate complexes in N,N-dimethyl formamide and found their reduction irreversible. Recently, Singh *et al*^{12,13} have determined polarographically the composition and stability constants of Cd(II) and Zn(II) acetylacetonate complexes. A survey of literature reveals that polarographic behaviour of Pb(II) and Mn(II) in acetylacetonate has not been studied so far. The present study was, therefore, undertaken with a view to determining the composition and the stability of acetylacetonate complexes of Pb(II) and Mn(II).

Experimental

All chemicals used were of analytical reagent grade and their stock solutions were prepared in conductivity water. The strength of the solutions of Pb(NO₃)₂ and MnCl₂ was determined by standard methods. Acetylacetonate was a B.D.H., A.R. (England) product. The concentration of each depolarizer in the final solution to be polarographed was maintained at 1.0×10^{-8} M. NaClO₄ was used as a supporting electrolyte in the case of Mn(II) while NaNO₃ was used in the case of Pb(II), as Pb(II) formed a precipitate with sodium perchlorate. Requisite amount (0.001%) of Triton X-100 was added in each case to suppress the maxima. The studies were done at a constant ionic strength $\mu=0.1$ (NaNO₃ or NaClO₄) and constant temperature ($25 \pm 0.1^\circ$) and a constant pH. Purified nitrogen was passed through the solutions to remove the dissolved oxygen. Polarograms of the solutions were taken using a manual polarograph, Toshniwal CLO2, in conjunction with a Toshniwal polyflex galvanometer PL 50. Saturated calomel electrode was used as a reference electrode. The capillary characteristics in the two systems have been mentioned in the respective Tables. The number of electrons 'n' involved in the reduction of acetyl-

acetate complexes was determined by millicoulometric method of DeVries and Kroon¹⁴ which gave the value of $n=2$ in each case. The concentration of acetylacetonate ion was calculated from the pH of the solution and the pK value of acetylacetonate as per the following equation :

$$K_a = \frac{[acac^-][H^+]}{[H acac]}$$

or $\log [acac^-] = pH + \log [H acac] - pK_a$

where, $[acac^-]$ is the concentration of free acetylacetonate ion and $[H acac]$ is the total concentration of acetylacetonate. The literature value of pK_a (8.95) has been used.

Results and Discussion

Pb(II)-acetylacetonate system :

The concentration of acetylacetonate was varied from 0-0.5 M. In each case a single well-defined and diffusion-controlled wave appeared. It is evident from Table 1 that $E_{1/2}$ is shifted to more negative

TABLE 1—POLAROGRAPHIC CHARACTERISTICS AND $F_j[X]$ FUNCTIONS OF Pb(II)-ACETYLACETONATE SYSTEM

$m^{2/3}t^{1/3} = 3.10 \text{ mg}^{2/3}\text{sec}^{-1/3}$ (in 0.1 M NaNO₃, open circuit)

$[acac^-] \times 10^5$ M	i_d μA	$-E_{1/2}$ (SCE) V	Slope mV	$F_0[X]$	$F_1[X] \times 10^{-3}$	$F_2[X] \times 10^{-3}$
0	11.95	0.400	30	—	—	—
2.24	11.95	0.410	31	2.18	0.52	—
4.46	11.78	0.420	30	4.82	0.85	0.79
6.60	11.12	0.430	30	11.12	1.53	1.56
11.22	11.12	0.440	32	24.26	2.07	1.99
22.44	10.95	0.450	32	53.70	2.35	0.82
33.66	10.46	0.460	32	122.46	3.61	0.92
44.88	10.29	0.470	31	271.64	6.03	1.23

potentials with increasing concentrations of acetylacetonate thereby showing the complex formation. The slope values of log plots (Table 1) are of the order of 31 ± 1 mV, showing that the reduction is reversible. The plot of $E_{1/2}$ vs $\log [acac^-]$ is a smooth curve thereby indicating the formation of successive complexes. DeFord and Hume's method¹⁵ has been applied for the determination of composition and stability constants of the complexes. An analysis of $F_j[X]$ functions reveals the formation of two successive complex species, $[Pb(acac)]^+$ and $[Pb(acac)_2]$ with stability constants $\log \beta_1 = 4.69$ and $\log \beta_2 = 9.08$.

Mn(II)-acetylacetonate system :

Polarograms of the solutions containing 1.0×10^{-3} M Mn(II) and borax buffer of pH 9.2 and also in the absence of the buffer were taken at the same ionic strength, $\mu=0.1$. Studies were conducted in an inert atmosphere (nitrogen) in order to ward off the possibility of the oxidation of Mn(II) to Mn(III) at this pH. It was observed that $E_{1/2}$ of Mn(II) in both the cases was the same. This shows that the negative shift in $E_{1/2}$ occurring in the presence of

increasing concentrations of acetylacetonate was solely due to complex formation between Mn(II) and acetylacetonate. In each case a single well-defined and diffusion-controlled wave appeared. In the absence of the ligand the slope of the log plot for Mn(II) is 45 mV (Table 2) which indicates¹⁶ that the reduction of Mn(II) is quasi-reversible. However, the slope values in the presence of acetylacetonate lie in the 60-66 mV range (Table 2). These are much

TABLE 2—POLAROGRAPHIC CHARACTERISTICS AND $F_j[X]$ FUNCTIONS OF Mn(II)-ACETYLACETONATE SYSTEM

$m^{2/3}t^{1/3} = 2.11 \text{ mg}^{2/3}\text{sec}^{-1/3}$ (in 0.1 M NaClO₄, open circuit)

$[acac^-] \times 10^3$ M	i_d μA	$-E_{1/2}$ (SCE) V	$-E_{1/2}^r$ (SCE) V	Slope mV	$F_0[X]$	$F_1[X] \times 10^{-3}$	$F_2[X] \times 10^{-3}$	$F_3[X] \times 10^{-3}$
0	8.18	1.490	1.480	45	—	—	—	—
1.0	7.92	1.590	1.502	66	5.73	4.73	—	—
2.0	7.92	1.540	1.514	66	14.61	6.80	—	—
4.0	7.65	1.550	1.525	62	250.32	62.33	145.8	31.4
6.0	7.04	1.560	1.532	61	593.06	98.67	157.7	22.9
8.0	6.60	1.570	1.540	60	1379.43	172.30	210.3	23.7

larger than the theoretical value expected for a 2-electron reversible reduction process. It is therefore inferred¹⁷ that the reduction of Mn(II) is irreversible in presence of acetylacetonate. The reversible half-wave potentials, $E_{1/2}^r$, has been calculated by Gellings¹⁸ method and the values are presented in Table 2. A plot of $E_{1/2}^r$ vs $\log [acac^-]$ is a smooth curve thereby showing the formation of successive complexes. DeFord and Hume's method has been applied for the calculation of composition and stability constants of successive complexes. An analysis of $F_j[X]$ functions (Table 2) reveals the formation of three successive complexes, $[Mn(acac)]^+$, $[Mn(acac)_2]$ and $[Mn(acac)_3]^-$, with $\log \beta_1 = 2.60$, $\log \beta_2 = 4.30$ and $\log \beta_3 = 6.30$.

On comparing the stability constants of mono and bis-complexes of Pb(II) and Mn(II) it is inferred that Pb(II) complexes are more stable than the Mn(II) ones. This is in harmony with the view of Mellor and Maley¹⁹ according to which the stability of the complexes of bivalent metal ions follows the order Pd > Cu > Ni > Pb > Co > Zn > Cd > Fe > Mn > Mg irrespective of the nature of the ligand involved.

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Ion Exchange Behaviour of Some Lanthanides and Actinides on the Derivatives of Polyvalent Metal Salt : Titanium Arsenomolybdate

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LITERATURE reveals that these days the characteristics of inorganic ion exchange materials are being credited towards achieving separations of lanthanides, actinides, heavy metals and of radiochemical interest. It has been also found that the derivatives of polyvalent metal salts are superior to their simple salts. Titanium phosphosilicate (TPS)¹, zirconium titaniumphosphate (ZTP)^{2,3} and zirconium phosphosilicate (ZPS)⁴ have been employed for the separations of some rare earths and fission products from mineral acids.

In continuation of earlier studies⁵⁻¹² on ion exchange materials of polyvalent metals, this is a part of extended approach towards their derivatives. The present report deals with the synthesis, characterisation and ion exchange behaviour of titanium arsenomolybdate. Its analytical potentiality has been explored with the quantitative separations of lanthanides from heavy metals.

Experimental

Titanium tetrachloride (B. D. H., England), arsenic acid (B. D. H.), ammonium molybdate (E. Merck) and other reagents were used of analytical grade.

The following instruments were used; Spekol u.v., Philips pH meter, Perkin Elmer spectrophotometer, muffle furnace and electric shaker.

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Synthesis of titanium arsenomolybdate (TAM) :

TAM was prepared by adding 0.15 M TiCl₄ solution to a mixture of 0.2 M arsenic acid and ammonium molybdate containing a few ml sulphuric acid in different volume ratios as indicated in Table 1. pH of the mixture was adjusted by the addition of ammonia. The remaining part of the synthesis was similar to that for other ion exchange materials.

Chemical composition :

200 mg of TAM (S₄) was dissolved in conc. H₂SO₄ and HCl. Titanium¹³ with 4-hydroxy phenyl arsenic acid and molybdenum as molybdenum¹⁰ sulphide were determined gravimetrically while arsenic¹⁴ was determined titrimetrically. The mole ratio in the sample was found as Ti : As : Mo :: 2.2 : 1 : 1.6.

Dissolution of TAM (S₄) :

100 mg of the exchanger was taken in 50 ml of the solution concerned. After shaking for 6 hr the undissolved part of the exchanger was removed by filtration. Titanium¹⁵, arsenic¹⁶ and molybdenum¹⁷ were determined spectrophotometrically.

Distribution studies :

The distribution coefficients K_d on TAM (S₄) phase were determined in DMW and 0.1 M HNO₃ solution as usual. The loading for cations was less than 3% of the ion exchange capacity. Uranium was determined spectrophotometrically while the other cations were titrated with 2 mM EDTA solution.

pH titration :

pH titrations were performed by Topper and Peppor method¹⁹. The material exhibited monofunctional behaviour.

Heat treatment :

Sample S₄ was treated at different temperatures in muffle furnace for 1 hr and ion exchange capacities (i. e. c.) were found to be 1.48 meq/g at 40° and 0.22 meq/g at 600°. IR spectra of the samples heated at different temperatures were taken by KBr disc method.

Column operation :

For separation studies 30×0.3 cm bore glass column was used and 1.00 g TAM (S₄) was kept in column with glass wool support. The rate of flow was 9 to 10 drops per min.

Results and Discussion

Various samples of TAM have been prepared at different pH and in different mixing ratios. Table 1 shows that the material attains high i.e.c. at higher pH. I.E.C. decreases on refluxing in arsenic acid and this might be due to the formation of new phases of TAM. On refluxing, the material turns towards powdery form while the unrefluxed material